

The 2025 seismicity burst in the Santorini – Amorgos seismovolcanic zone

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Introduction

In January 2025, an intense earthquake activity started in the Santorini volcano area, southern Aegean, causing great concern among the local population and resulting in actions such as school closures and spontaneous evacuation. Seismic activity and geodetic motion increased inside the Santorini caldera in the last second half of 2024, intensifying in mid-January 2025 and extending offshore to the northeast around the Anydros islet between Santorini and Amorgos islands. This activity was remarkably dense, with turbulent variations over space and time (Figure 1). Up to 13 March 2025 over 4000 earthquakes exceeding $M1.0$ occurred and analyzed.

Santorini is an active stratovolcano in the volcanic arc of the Hellenic subduction zone, with several smaller craters in addition to a main caldera, which collapsed around 1625 BC (known as Minoan eruption). Volcanic centers (volcanoes, fumaroles or solfatara fields), epicenters of strong shallow earthquakes (with focal depths up to 20 km) and epicenters of intermediate depth strong earthquakes (with focal depths between 120 and 160 km) in the southern Aegean volcanic arc can be grouped into five well defined, linear clusters trending about $N60^{\circ}E$, corresponding to five extensional zones (Papazachos and Panagiotopoulos, 1993).

Regional seismicity is mostly low-rate crustal activity. However, the largest instrumental earthquake in Greece during the 20th century is an $Mw7.7$ rupture in 1956 (Pacheco and Sykes, 1992), just south of Amorgos Island, caused extensive destruction in the southern Aegean. The earthquake ruptured an ENE–striking normal fault that lies parallel to the southern coastline of Amorgos (Papadimitriou et al., 2005). The area of the 2025 swarm coincides with the rupture area of the $M6.9$ main shock, that occurred 13 minutes after the first 1956 $M_w7.7$ main shock.

Relocated microseismicity recorded by a temporary network deployed in 2003 to investigate microseismicity of the Santorini volcanic center, revealed two clusters. The main cluster was located at the Columbo Reef, which is the top of a submarine volcano, whereas a smaller cluster was located near the Anydros islet, without seismicity inside Santorini caldera, both clusters were aligned in a NE–SW direction (Dimitriadis et al., 2009). During February 2011 an intense microseismicity was initiated within the caldera and lasted until March 2012. In addition to increased seismicity, the volcano showed significant ground uplift, reaching 14 cm within this period (Foumelis et al., 2013). Manual analysis and relocation provided high-resolution image of the activated fault segments (Papadimitriou et al., 2015). The NE–SW activity inside the caldera, with dextral strike slip motion, was rapidly diminished after the activation of an offshore area to its southwest. Normal faulting activity expanded to the northeast offshore area, near Anydros, where the 2025 swarm is manifested. Since 2012, the activity inside the caldera was low and with relative quiescent periods, whereas near Columbo it has been more frequent and continuous (Karakostas and Papadimitriou, 2025).

High-precision earthquake locations

We used the NLL algorithm (Lomax et al., 2000, 2014) and the multiscale high precision NLL–SSST–coherence procedure (Lomax and Savvaidis, 2022) to relocate a manually picked set of earthquakes with data taken from the bulletins from the Geophysics Department of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (doi:10.7914/SN/HT) and National Observatory of Athens (doi:10.7914/SN/HL) and a set of picks obtained with machine learning (ML). For the relocation of the manually picked earthquakes the recordings of 31 seismic stations were used. Fourteen of them were in operation on Santorini Island since the beginning of our study (January 2024). Seven stations were installed or started their operation after long interruption in February 2025 [Anydros (Feb. 03), Anafi and Amorgos (Feb. 04), Gavrilos (Feb. 07), Astypalaia (Feb. 10), Ios (Feb. 12), Christiana (Feb. 26)]. For the ML picking we analysed waveform data during 1 January–28 February 2025, from 21 broadband stations located in distances up to 120 km from the seismicity centroid (<https://eida.gein.noa.gr/>). The earthquake detection and phase picking were performed by Phasenet (Zhu and Beroza, 2018), a deep–neural–network–based arrival-time picker. Phase picks are then associated using the REAL software (Zhang et al., 2019). REAL is a grid–search phase association algorithm that performs phase association and an initial location of earthquakes, primarily through counting the number of P

and S picks that appear within a travel–time curve threshold determined by the user and secondarily from travel time residuals (Zhang et al., 2019).

Figure 1. Seismicity evolution in map views for consecutive time windows as indicated inside each snapshot. The size of the symbols is proportional to the earthquake magnitude.

Relocated manually picked seismicity is shown in the maps of Figure 1, covering consecutive time intervals. Background seismicity during 2024 exhibits quite shallow clustering inside Santorini caldera (pink symbols), more dense clustering around the Columbo reef (offshore area NE of Santorini Island) with seismicity up to ~10 km deep, and a third cluster, along with sparse activity, to the northeast and around Anydros islet with focal depths in the brittle crust (5–15 km, inside the seismogenic layer of the back–arc Aegean area, Hatzfeld et al., 1999; among others) with the majority of them getting focal depths between 6–12 km.

With the Machine Learning detection and picking we obtained a catalog with 34442 earthquakes. We relocated the detected seismicity using the same procedure as the manually picked catalogue (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Relocated seismicity during 01/01/2025–28/02/2025 using machine learning detection and NLL-coherence location. The red and yellow stars depict the epicenters of the 1956 M7.7 and M6.9 main shocks, respectively (Bondar et al., 2015; ISC, 2024).

Discussion

Seismic activity intensified during the first weeks of 2025 (1–26 January), including mainly small magnitude seismic activity within the caldera at shallow depths. The main activity abruptly jumped to the northeast offshore area during 27–31 January. Beginning on 1 and up to 4 February, an unusually high number of moderate magnitude earthquakes occurred, the most intense ever reported during the instrumental era anywhere in Greece, with three earthquakes of $M \geq 5.0$ and eighty with $M \geq 4.0$. The activity formed a ~20 km-long NE–SW trend, in accordance with the strike of the 1956 second main shock ($M 6.9$).

The epicentral area of the 2025 swarm was strictly confined within the Anydros basin, which is bounded on both sides by NE–SW striking normal faults. It appears that further migration of the activity along the Amorgos fault zone almost ceased. The shallower focal depths occupy the southwestern part of the seismicity zone, where NE–SW trending small volcanic cones are also located. Over the next two days (on 5 and 6 February) the main seismicity to the northeast became slightly more compact, with 47 (forty-seven) $M 4+$ earthquakes, and around 10 km depth, whereas activity near Columbo decreased. Between 7 and 9 February, 39 (thirty-nine) $M 4+$ earthquakes were concentrated in an even more localized area, but sparser seismicity extends as far as 40 km NE of Santorini. Two additional $M 5+$ earthquakes struck on 10 and 12 February, with the $M 4+$ occurrence rate appearing to decline. The main concentration of activity from 10–11 February migrated and jumped to over 10 km NE of Anydros Island, before rapidly returning back to the SW of Anydros by 12 February. During these last days, when the $M 4+$ activity was more constrained we could distinguish multiple small structures within the fault network that hosts the seismicity burst.

By 13 February, seismic activity had dramatically decreased, to only a few $M 4+$ earthquakes per day, and the last recorded $M 5+$ earthquake on 17 February. From 13 February and through at least 13 March (Figure 1), small clusters took place to the north and eastern edges of the activated area.

Coulomb seismicity–stress imaging of the swarm

The 3D, scalar ΔCFS field due to finite–fault slip or dike opening can be obtained through integration over the fault or dike of the point–source ΔCFS field of stresses due to a point shear dislocation or tensile opening in an elastic half–space (Haskell 1964; Kikuchi & Kanamori 1982; Okada 1992; King et al. 1994; Materna & Wong 2023). This procedure is a forward calculation, with the resulting ΔCFS field often assessed by how well it agrees with the surrounding distribution of seismicity. The corresponding inverse problem is to infer a distribution of finite–fault slip or dike opening given the 3D distribution of aftershocks or other seismicity and the physics of the Coulomb failure stress criteria. Here we infer the space–time distribution of fault slip or dike opening through an imaging methodology: for specified point source slip or dike opening and receiver fault orientations, we obtain 3D maps of extended slip or dike opening through correlation of point–source ΔCFS kernels across the spatial distribution of seismicity. This seismicity–stress procedure finds a 3D distribution of relative fault slip or dike opening which can explain, in accordance with the physics of the Coulomb failure stress criteria, the surrounding distribution of seismicity.

We performed Coulomb seismicity – stress imaging (Lomax, 2025) of the 2025 Santorini – Amorgos earthquake swarm to determine whether the swarm activity could be driven by ΔCFS either from pure normal faulting source (Figure 3) or a vertical dike source with tensile opening (Figure 4). The results for the normal faulting source (Figure 3) show broad lobes of maximum source potential which are separated from and extend far to the northwest and southeast of the swarm seismicity, and which are

not parallel to the steep, 65°SE dip of the target normal faulting source. Seismicity-stress imaging supports a given source and receiver configuration when the maximum source potential is a) concentrated within the seismicity distribution and in areas of no or low seismicity, and b) flattened and extended parallel to a source fault or fracture plane orientation. Thus, these seismicity-stress imaging results do not support extended normal faulting as a driver of the swarm seismicity.

Figure 3. Seismicity-stress imaging of the 2025 Santorini-Amorgos swarm seismicity using a pure normal faulting source specified by a representative mechanism for the M_w 7.7, 1956 Amorgos earthquake from Brüstle et al. (2014; strike N36°E, dip 65°SE, rake -102°). 3D density clouds of relative amplitudes of the high-potential portions of the imaged seismicity-stress finite-source fields (yellow and red show normalized correlation ≥ 0.8 and ≥ 0.7 , respectively) are shown in a) map view, b) profile view from the SE, and c) profile view from the SW. Dots show NLL-SC-ML relocated swarm seismicity from 2025-01-01 through 2025-02-28, color coded according to occurrence time. Light red lines show mapped surface faults (NOAFaults v6.0); blue inverted pyramids show seismic stations used for ML picking and NLL-SC relocation.

In contrast, the 3D maps of seismicity-stress imaging over the swarm seismicity for a vertical tensile source (Figure 4) show an elongated volume of highest source potential that is mainly below and partly surrounded by the seismicity, abuts high-density limits of the seismicity, is aligned parallel to the trend of the swarm, and is flattened towards a vertical plane. All of these characteristics are compatible with and support a vertical, opening fracture or dyke as a stress source that causes the swarm seismicity.

Figure 4. Seismicity-stress imaging of the 2025 Santorini-Amorgos swarm seismicity for a dike source with tensile opening on vertical planes. 3D density clouds of relative amplitudes of the high-potential portions of the imaged seismicity-stress finite-source fields (yellow and red show normalized correlation ≥ 0.8 and ≥ 0.7 , respectively) are shown in a) map view, b) profile view from the SE, and c) profile view from the SW. Dots show NLL-SC-ML relocated swarm seismicity from 2025-01-01 through 2025-02-28, color coded according to occurrence time. Light red lines show mapped surface faults (NOAFaults v6.0); blue inverted pyramids show seismic stations used for ML picking and NLL-SC relocation.

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